

[研究文章 Research Article]

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Sympetrum parvulum (Bartenev, 1913) (Odonata: Libellulidae): A Newly Recorded Dragonfly from Matsu Islands, Taiwan

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Abstract: The genus *Sympetrum* on Matsu Islands, Taiwan is summarized, and further records of *S. fonscolombii* (Selys, 1840) are provided. *Sympetrum cordulegaster* (Selys, 1883) and *S. depressiusculum* (Selys, 1841) are newly reported from the islands. Additionally, *Sympetrum parvulum* (Bartenev, 1913) is reported from Taiwan for the first time. The status of the *S. parvulum* in Taiwan is considered as an occasionally migrated record.

Key word: Dragonfly, vagrant dragonfly, migration, east Palearctic, Oriental, new record

Introduction

The genus *Sympetrum* of Taiwan has been reviewed by Ma et al. (2022) in which ten species were recorded, including three resident species, three vagrant species, and four species that are either extinct or of unknown status. The Matsu Islands (Lienchiang County), located off the eastern coast of Fujian Province, share a similar fauna and flora with the mainland. Recent reports of new dragonfly records from the Matsu Islands indicate that the fauna of these islands remains poorly surveyed (Hu et al. 2023). Within the genus *Sympetrum*, only *S. fonscolombii* (Selys, 1840) has been reported from the islands (Ma et al. 2022). In the present paper, we summarize the current records of the genus on the Matsu Islands and report *Sympetrum cordulegaster* (Selys, 1883), *S. depressiusculum* (Selys, 1841) and *Sympetrum parvulum* (Bartenev, 1913) as newly recorded from the islands, with the latter is also being a new addition to the Taiwanese fauna.

Materials and methods

The photos were taken using a Canon EOS R5 camera body with either an RF100mm f/2.8L MACRO IS USM lens or an RF100-500mm f/4.5-7.1L IS USM lens and subsequently edited in Adobe Photoshop CS5. The voucher specimens are deposited at the Taiwan Forestry Research Institute, Taipei, Taiwan (TFRI). In cases where the record was based only on photos, it is referred to in the section “Photo records”. The body length, abdomen length and hind wings length of *S. parvulum* were measured using an electronic digital vernier caliper.

Results

紅脈蜻蛉

Sympetrum fonscolombii (Selys, 1840)

Material examination. TAIWAN: Lienchiang County: 1 female, Nangan Township, Chenggongshan Cemetery (成功山民眾公墓), 26.1529, 119.9427, 30-IX-2023, leg. Lee et al. (TFRI).

Photo records. TAIWAN: Lienchiang County: 1 male, Nangan Township, 13-XI-2017, obs. C.-C. Hsu; 1 male, Dongyin Agricultural Research and Extension Station (東引農業改良場), 26.3598, 120.4853, 14-X-2020, obs. F.-S. Tseng.

Distribution.

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Ma et al. (2022) summarized the distribution of this species in Taiwan; it is newly recorded from Dongyin Township.

長尾蜻蜒

Sympetrum cordulegaster (Selys, 1883)

Photo records. TAIWAN: Lienchiang County: 1 male and 1 female, Dongyin Agricultural Research and Extension Station (東引農業改良場), 26.3598, 120.4853, 14-X-2020, obs. F.-S. Tseng; 1 male, ditto, 24-IX-2023, obs. F.-S. Tseng.

Distribution.

Ma et al. (2022) summarized the distribution of this species in Taiwan; it is newly recorded from Lienchiang County.

秋紅蜻蜒

Sympetrum depressiusculum (Selys, 1841)

Material examination. TAIWAN: Lienchiang County: 1 male, Beigan Township, 26.2321, 119.9937, 28-IX-2023, leg. Lee et al. (TFRI).

Photo records. TAIWAN: Lienchiang County: 1 male, Dongyin Township, Dongyin Agricultural Research and Extension Station (東引農業改良場), 26.3598, 120.4853, 23-IX-2023, obs. F.-S. Tseng; 2 females, ditto, 24-IX-2023, obs. F.-S. Tseng; 1 male, Dongyin Township, Dongyin Command Museum (東引指揮部隊史館), 26.3643, 120.4937, 24-IX-2023, obs. F.-S. Tseng; 1 male and 1 female, Beigan Township, Wusha Reservoir (午沙水庫), 26.2193, 119.9841, 28-IX-2023, obs. Lee et al.; 1 male and 1 female, Nangan Township, Shengtian Marsh (勝天草澤), 26.1492, 119.9116, 30-IX-2023, obs. Lee et al.

Distribution.

Ma et al. (2022) summarized the distribution of this species in Taiwan; it is newly recorded from Lienchiang County.

姬紅蜻蜒

Sympetrum parvulum (Bartenev, 1913)

(Figs 1–2)

Material examination. TAIWAN: Lienchiang County: 1 male, Nangan Township, Shengtian Marsh (勝天草澤), 26.1492, 119.9116, 30-IX-2023, leg. Lee et al. (TFRI).

Measurements. Body length: 35.44 mm; abdomen length: 23.84 mm; hind wing length: 26.63 mm.

Diagnosis. In Taiwan, the species is similar to *S. eroticum ardens* (MaLachlan, 1894) and *S. cordulegaster* (Selys, 1883). The male can be distinguished from *S. eroticum ardens* by absence of distinct black spots on face, and from *S. cordulegaster* by lack of extended margin on abdominal segment VII.

Habitat. The male was found in a grassy pond adjacent to a secondary forest (Fig. 2). The pond was densely covered with Southern Cut Grass (*Leersia hexandra*) and Common Water Hyacinth (*Pontederia crassipes*) mixed with a few Narrow-leaved Cattail (*Typha angustifolia*).

Distribution.

The species is widely distributed in China (Henan, Hubai, Hunan, Guizhou, Chongqing, Fujian, Guangdong), Russia (Far East), Korea and Japan (Zhang, 2019; Ozono et al., 2022). It is reported from Taiwan for the first time in this study.

Comments.

In Japan and China, *S. parvulum* was regarded as a resident species, with no migration record has been reported (Zhang 2019, Ozono et al. 2022). Moreover, a mark-recapture experiment indicated that the species has a limited active range (Watanabe & Taguchi 1988). Despite multiple surveys in the same area, we found only find a single male, which we consider *S. parvulum* as an occasional vagrant from Fujian, China.

Figure 1. Male *Sympetrum parvulum* (Bartenev, 1913). A – dorsal habitus; B – lateral habitus; C – face; D – live photo.

Figure 2. Habitat of *Sympetrum parvulum* (Bartenev, 1913) on Matsu Islands.

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姬紅蜻蛉（蜻蛉目：蜻蛉科）：臺灣馬祖列島新紀錄蜻蛉

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摘要: 本文總結了臺灣馬祖群島的赤蜻屬 (*Sympetrum*) 分佈現況，並提供紅脈蜻蛉 (*S. fonscolombii*) 的新觀察紀錄。文中首次報導出現於馬祖群島上的長尾蜻蛉 (*S. cordulegaster*)、秋紅蜻蛉 (*S. depressiusculum*) 與姬紅蜻蛉 (*S. parvulum*)，其中姬紅蜻蛉為臺灣新紀錄，但被認為是偶然的遷徙紀錄。

關鍵詞: 蜻蛉、迷蜓、遷移、東古北區、東方區、新紀錄種